

Manual Prototype Partnership 1.0

DELIVERABLE 2.3

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Executive summary

This deliverable aims to offer the future Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems a Manual 1.0 that helps the guidance of its activities. This has been further refined into specific objectives:

- Carry out four in-depth case studies to get recommendations for the manual (Chapter 5, section 5.1)
- Extract recommendations from work packages for the Manual, including reflections on an ideal partnership from a private sector perspective, relation with Education, Trade-offs, a large number of collected case studies, and Communication Actions (Chapter 5, sections 5.2 – 5.7)
- Align recommendations with the main Prototype Elements in a table, that will become the backbone of the Manual Prototype 1.0 (chapter 6).

This Manual will be further elaborated with the FOODPathS team to get a final version (2.0) at the end of its project duration.

The main elements of the Milestone 5, partly modified thanks to insights described in D2.3, are:

- Vision & sustainable value creation, addressing sustainability consequently from the three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic)
- Governance and legal status of a partnership, incorporating balanced bottom-up and top-down decision-making processes, cross-scales and multi-stakeholder group interactions, and flexibility as well as adaptability in structures and functions.
- Co-funding mechanisms & funders forum, aligning of funding strategies and priorities of diverse funders while following food system approaches.
- Modus operandi, favoring collective intelligence and systemic approaches in all operations including human resources, finance, communication, etc.
- Activity areas as defined in the SRIA, with particular attention to:
 - Sticking to the 4 thematic areas (change the way we eat, process & supply, connect and govern) and their links, considering them all from a Food Systems lens and connecting R&I to Science-to-Policy advice and Education programs (RIPE concept)
 - Further elaborating the 4 transversal areas: funding (already mentioned above as separate bullet point), observatory, Hub of FS labs (working on co-creation cases), and knowledge sharing.
- Potential trade-offs and co-benefits, involving and taking into account the feedback from Mirror Groups, transition needs of various actor groups, inter-continental conflicting issues, and other ways of knowledge generation such as indigenous knowledge.
- Communication, dissemination & exploitation, generating a snowball effect that motivates divers FS actors to join forces to reach sustainability outcomes.
- Cooperation with other partnerships, large initiatives, and EU projects like CLEVERFOOD, realizing that sustainability outcomes cannot be reached from only post-farming and -fishing perspectives and that issues are far too complex to be resolved internally.

Figure 1 The key elements of the prototype Partnership, presented as a bird, forming a flock with other Partnerships and large scale initiatives to accelerate the transition towards SFS. Communication is then primordial; Modified design from H. Schepers & H. de Vries

This has resulted in the following, adapted image of the Prototype, see Figure 1. Future insights may change this image further, e.g. taking into account mirroring and reflection by others, science-to-policy insights, and food system approaches in funding. It most likely leads to **different 'ideal' – context-specific – partnerships**. Hence, one may better consider **a flock of partnerships** that jointly fly in the appropriate direction to reach sustainability outcomes (see figure 1).

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1. Background

Milestone 5 aimed to describe the key elements of the prototype Partnership that need to be elaborated in 2023-2024. These elements are detailed here in Deliverable 2.3, describing the very first version of the Manual for the Future Partnership on SFS.

During a meeting in Rome on the 27th of June 2023, members of the FOODPathS consortium and its Advisory Board gave input. Major remarks concerned (i) developing a coherent strategy following a reversed chain approach (starting with the consumer, society, and markets; these are typical for a post-farming & -fishing oriented Partnership), (ii) adding communication as a key element (both internal as well as external to the Partnership), (iii) distinguishing but also connecting external call activities and internal Partnership actions, and (iv) including the global context, because the European food playing field is globally-oriented due to trade.

Since a manual for the future Partnership includes findings from work packages in FOODPathS, a synthesis of a first series of main findings is here included, while details can be found in the specific deliverable reports of each WP. These are preceded by lessons learned from four in-depth case studies as performed in WP2; these lessons learned are quite detailed, even though the fully described interviews – with 10 interviewed actors per in-depth case study – are here not included. Generic lessons learned from all case studies are included in chapter 6 and, together with insights of WPs, related to the main elements of the prototype partnership.

2. Introduction

FOODPathS aims to design a prototype for the future Sustainable Food Systems (SFS) Partnership in Europe. This prototype will offer a concrete pathway on how future partnerships should function from 2024 onwards, covering all its components and including a **manual** based on the experience gained during the FOODPathS project; as here elaborated in Deliverable 2.3.

The Prototype will include co-funding strategies, a governance model, a *Modus Operandi*, a sustainability charter, a strategic research and innovation agenda (SRIA), and a series of co-creation cases, among others. Potential trade-offs of proposed activities, including effective communication, dissemination and exploitation (C&D&E) strategies – resulting from the efforts of involving local and global stakeholders in shaping future partnership – will be proposed as examples to be pursued.

The Lay-Out of the Prototype P-SFS covers many different aspects as already described in the Horizon Europe Call text for FOODPathS. FOODPathS partners have unravelled the call topic needs and regrouped them as major building blocks of the prototype Partnership. This process was called ‘the Spaghetti exercise’, as presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. 'Spaghetti exercise', regrouping call needs as key building blocks of a Prototype Partnership; Source: the authors.

In addition, the Narrative (SCAR, 2021), Template (SCAR, 2022), and Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda (SCAR, 2023) of the Partnership SFS served to verify if our selected key elements of the prototype are relevant. A major observation was that there is a need to link the SRIA to Science-to-Policy processes and education programs. Hence the RIPE concept (Research, Innovation, science-to-Policy, and Education) was introduced by FOODPathS. This is currently further elaborated in work package (WP) 6, see Figure 3.

Figure 3. The Research, Innovation, science-to-Policy, and Education (RIPE) concept; authors design

The word 'inclusiveness' is crucial in the Call – hence for the prototype Partnership SFS. **Inclusiveness means that nobody is left behind.** This should come back in the constitution of partnerships and all its activities and governing actions; still, inclusiveness does not automatically mean that a partnership is also able to function and reach sustainability outcomes and include all actors without ending up in chaos. This is what FOODPathS tries to understand. Therefore, our FOODPathS Consortium has been built upon

Another advantage of the FOODPathS Consortium is that it can **mobilize a wide range of diverse experts across Europe** and even globally, hence studying **numerous food system cases**. These have been presented in Deliverable 2.1 (D2.1), and some first observations are included below in chapter 6.

For this deliverable, especially **four in-depth case studies of different kinds of 'partnerships'** have been performed and described in Chapter 5. Why? The selected in-depth case studies cover local to EU-wide scales and reveal the functioning of very different partnerships, their sustainability visions and objectives, their way of governing, and joint value creation. Since for each case, ten interviews with different involved actors have been carried out, a multi-actor view on a few partnerships has been obtained.

The ambition of FOODPathS remains to be **as open and inclusive as possible, hence to further collect insights from other FS cases** to provide the future SFS Partnership and other partnerships with well-evidenced options.

The enormous challenge of reaching sustainability outcomes for a large number of interacting complex food systems requires – next to inclusiveness – the consideration of **collective intelligence approaches**. **This is further elaborated in WP2, task 2.3 'Modus Operandi'**. Since this task started recently, findings will be included in the final version of this Deliverable in Month 36.

After the presentation of the insights obtained from the different WPs, the insights have been translated into a first set of recommendations. In the next project year, these recommendations will be further fuelled by insights obtained in the WPs and by discussions with experts in collaborative actions.

3. Objectives of the Deliverable

The main objective of this deliverable report is to offer the future Partnership Consortium a first version manual that helps its guidance of activities carried out by the Partnership. This has been further refined into 5 specific objectives, with corresponding actions undertaken to reach this deliverable.

	Objectives of D2.3	Main actions undertaken for D2.3
1.	Carry out a limited number of in-depth case studies to extract recommendations for the Manual.	INRAE has carried out these in-depth case studies, together with IRWIR-PAN/BIOEAST, Cariplo, and SEAMK.
2.	Extract recommendations from WPs for the Prototype, including reflections on an ideal partnership from a private sector perspective, relation with Education, Trade-offs, collected case studies, and Communication Actions.	WP leaders EFFoST, ICLEI, and EUFIC have provided input from their WPs; A specific section on an ideal partnership has been prepared by Confagricoltura; FOODPathS partners in WP4&7 have collected and analyzed 50+ co-creation cases, this has led to a (published) review paper
3.	Align recommendations with the main Prototype Elements and prepare a first table of a structured set of recommendations for the Prototype P-SFS, i.e. Manual Prototype 1.0	A first draft is here prepared by all contributors and serves as the basis for the Manual Prototype Partnership
4.	Reporting the deliverable with specific attention to the 'manual' character of the deliverable	D2.3 coordinator / INRAE team

Table 1 - Objectives and main actions implemented

4. Target audience

The target audience is the future Partnership Consortium, the EC DG RTD, and the SCAR SWG FS. For the final version of the manual also other actors – involved in any large initiative in the broad domain of sustainable food systems, and the wider bioeconomy – will be actively approached. This also includes the members of the FOODPathS networks, represented by its partners and its Advisory Board members.

5. Methods and results

5.1. In-depth case studies (WP2)

5.1.1. Methodology of the in-depth case study

After collecting 72 examples of food system cases (D2.1), which reveal all kinds of ‘partnerships’, with the support of the WP4 and WP7 partners, in-depth case studies were conducted on 4 ‘partnerships’. These reflect the diversity of scales and cover countries in the north, south, east, and west of Europe:

- ❖ Neighborhood Hubs Against Food Waste (urban, city of Milan),
- ❖ Pôle Mer Méditerranée (regional, France),
- ❖ Foodwest (regional/national, Finland) and
- ❖ BIOEAST (cross-countries, Central-Eastern countries of European Union).

Concretely, 10 interviews per case have been carried out in 2023 among diverse actors of each partnership regarding what could be learned from their governance model, the actors involved, the value co-created, and the sustainability vision. The interview guide is given in Annex 1.

A short description of the four cases:

Neighbourhood Hubs Against Food Waste (shortened in MC for Milan Case)

Within the context of the Milan World Expo, the Milan Urban Food Policies in 2015 have been created and supported by the newly established partnership between the Milan City Hall and the Cariplo Foundation. A working group has been set up to activate synergies between different political domains of food systems. In 2016, operational activities on food recovery and redistribution started, galvanized by the recent Gadda Law on a fiscal incentive for food donation. The theme was supported by the new, fourfold partnership that signed the Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) “Zero Waste”. The four partners are the Milan City Hall, the Cariplo Foundation, the Politecnico of Milan, and Assolombardia (the regional branch of the Italian business association Confindustria). The key main idea underlying the project was to create a centralizing space for the collection of food surpluses from different sources – i.e. food retailers and firms’ canteens – and where to redistribute it to a network of NGOs distributing food aid to families in need. <https://www.comune.milano.it/en/-/food.-policy.-inaugurato-il-nuovo-hub-di-quartiere-contro-lo-spreco-alimentare-di-piazzale-selinunte>

Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM)

PMM can be described as an innovation cluster covering two regions along the French Mediterranean coast. These regions are working together with their twin brother regions located in Britannia, on the Atlantic coast in France, united in the Pôle Mer Bretagne Atlantique. Both of them share the same objective: “building a carbon-free and sovereign blue economy, supporting sustainable growth and future jobs” (Pôle Mer Méditerranée, 2023). From this objective, the cluster derived 3 main ambitions: (i) enhancing innovation by structuring sectors, (ii) being a central point thanks to the connections and implementation of regional/national policies and (iii) promoting PMM’s members and their areas at the international level, while reinforcing its leadership within the Mediterranean basin.

PMM counts more than 500 members divided into 4 different categories: big companies, SMEs, research & education centers, and the larger ecosystem (including banks, consulting agencies, NGOs, and so on). <https://polemermediterranee.com/en/homepage/>

Foodwest

Foodwest is a medium-sized private company considered a major stakeholder in Finland today because its objective and creation context is unique. The services offered are quite broad, from the formulation of new recipes and packaging designs to studies on consumer behavior. They translate product ideas into concrete product concepts and then support their development, adding value to future products. It may not immediately be evident to consider Foodwest as a partnership, given its activities that are close to a consulting agency and its legal status as a private company. However, Foodwest is not a classical enterprise since it is more a shared service platform of national interest, driven by a partnership of universities, public institutions, and companies. Foodwest provides tools, solutions, and knowledge, and its owners/customers are providing the objectives, and are involved in a diverse set of activities. <https://foodwest.fi/en/front-page/>

BIOEAST

The first ambition of the BIOEAST Initiative is to voluntarily gather policymakers from 11 Central-Eastern European countries sharing the motivation to develop a circular, bioeconomy strategy in their countries. Their mission statement toward 2030 is the following: “to develop knowledge and cooperation based on circular bioeconomies, which helps to enhance their growth and to create new value-added jobs, especially in rural areas, maintaining or even strengthening environmental sustainability” (BIOEAST, 2024). The second ambition is to define bioeconomy clusters at different levels, from national to macro-regional scales, building a series of bioeconomy hubs. Each hub will serve as an established communication center on bioeconomy within BIOEAST countries. <https://bioeast.eu/>

The preliminary elements are described below and are summarized in **Table 1**; they are all based on the interviews. At this stage, not yet all results are finalized and analyzed; these will be presented in the second and final version of the manual. Then, we will also:

- i. Deepen reflections on topics such as risks and the reliability of future research on the functioning of these partnerships. For example, what if EU/regional funding ceases? How might the voices or demands of corporate shareholders impact the functioning of partnerships on SFS? Can these threats be reduced, and how? How can one measure the impacts of food system cases? Regarding knowledge sharing, can information be shared in the context of innovation activities, especially when discussing client-specific cases (confidentiality agreements, NDAs)?
- ii. Re-verify in more detail observations from the 70+ case studies in WP4, 5, and 7 (in particular including the draft publication submitted); here, we have presented the first major insights (section 5.5). It should be noted that these were not in-depth case studies, hence, a well-evidenced verification will not be possible.

A cross-check of these, and other questions, with the case studies performed will be future work.

		Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM)	Foodwest	BIOEAST	Neighbourhood Hubs Against Food Waste (NHAFW)
Main characteristics	Legal status of the initiative/partnership	Association (innovation cluster)	Private company	Grant Agreement	Memorandum of understanding (MOU) between Cariplo Foundation and Milan City Hall
	Scale of action	Regional	National	Cross-countries	Local (city)
	Main goals	To sustainably develop blue economy, including fisheries, through innovation	Enhancing Finnish food innovation	Gathering policymakers of some Central-Eastern countries toward a common bioeconomy strategy	To create a centralising space, where to collect food surpluses from different sources and where to redistribute it to a network of NGOs; they provide food aid to families in need
	Activities	Regional economic development projects, services for enhancing businesses' growth...	Formulation of new recipes, packaging design, consumer behaviour studies, process development...	Animation of working groups, SRIA elaboration, sub-national/regional bioeconomy hub building, new participants recruiting...	Food recovery and redistribution
	Context of creation	Regional blue economy dynamics + French Innovation Clusters receiving specific funds in 2005	Necessity identified by regional food companies + Finnish Innovation specific funds provided in 1995	Willingness of some European Development Network members to define a bioeconomy strategy for Central-Eastern Countries that are generally far less present in EU projects	Milan Food Pack dynamics in 2014 with creation of working group + law on fiscal incentives for food donations in 2016 via operational activities
Governance	Actors involved	Big companies, SMEs, research & education centers, larger ecosystem (NGOs, public sector, consulting agencies...)	Big companies, SMEs and start-ups, public sector (development agencies...), universities	Ministries for bioeconomy sectors and research, research institutes & universities (future expected participation: private sector)	The Milan city hall, Cariplo foundation, research, association of companies (part of the MOU)+ NGOs, canteens, retailers, volunteers (civil society)...
	Funds providers	Largest part from regional funds and members fees	Biggest part from selling services and a minor part from public funds	EU funds for supporting coordination and support action projects (i.e. Horizon 2020)	City facilities donations, private sponsorship, award prizes...
	Decision process	Democratic vote by the representatives of each actor's categories both for the board and projects selection; currently strategy plans are elaborated by PMM's teams	Strategic decisions by Foodwest team only, advised by the board and customers	Decisions on general directions of the Initiative by the board composed of representatives of Agriculture ministries of the 11 countries, advised by researchers (Thematic Working groups (TWG), projects outputs, external experts...)	The MOU gives a reference framework agreed upon by its members; but, a high flexibility is given to all the participants and a lot of decisions are informally made
	Type of governance model	Mostly participatory (each kind of actors represented)	Limited participatory (actors are voiced but do not vote for decisions)	Limited participatory (implementation of bioeconomy strategies is made at the political level)	Participatory and inclusive (all kind of actors represented)
Value co-creation	Key benefits being members	Anchorage for blue economy development, networking activities, services for projects development	Actively participating in food sector development in Finland, promoting regional/national know-how, enhancing research collaborations, networking opportunities, services for food innovation	Knowledge transfer, networking opportunities, setting up bioeconomy agendas	Resilience to shocks, social links, know-how (for the city food systems at large), increasing impact of each actor, stepping out of the lab and collecting data (for researchers), gaining in visibility and recognition, accessing international scale activities, increasing resources
	Value distribution among the participants	Each participant can equally benefit from PMM's services and is being voices	Services are accessible to every company even if they are not shareholders (possibility to receive some funds for smaller ones)	1st project (BIOEASTsUP) and TWGs outputs were mainly data relevant for BIOeast Initiative, less relevant for individual participants	Perceived equitable distribution of advantages obtained via synergistic actions
	Key benefits for the society at large	General improvement of the blue economy sectors toward sustainability, contribution to the regional economic stability	Food companies improvement toward sustainability, enhanced international influence of Finnish food product development, contribution to the regional/national economic stability	Adoption of a new mindset toward sustainable, in particular regarding handling of bioresources in Central-Eastern European countries, development of new skills/responsibilities in Central-Eastern countries	Limiting food waste at urban scale, building external know-how, reinforcing social links between professionals but also with the civil society (volunteers and beneficiaries)
	Barriers identified	Not every participant is aware of all the services proposed by PMM, lack of employees regarding the growing number of participants and activities, funds decreasing, ...	Fluctuation of political willingness to support innovation, inclusiveness of some actors (NGOs...), productions' line management and resource allocation...	The motivation of each participant is different from one another, TWG organisation and communication with the board/project, funds raising, language...	Low efficiency in coordination of large activities, competition dynamics, lonely drivers' attitudes, identity and visions conflicts
Sustainability	Sustainability vision	Blue economy itself embodies a sustainability vision, at the core of PMM's strategy - <i>Technological vision</i>	Even if not broadly promoted, sustainability is culturally integrated in Foodwest strategy - <i>Food science vision</i>	Bioeconomy itself embodies a sustainability vision at the core of BIOEAST strategy, yet it can be considered as too general in guidelines - <i>Political vision</i>	Improving food security while decreasing food waste - <i>Democratic local vision</i>

Table 2: Summary of main insights in four in-depth cases studied.

5.1.2. Preliminary observations (results)

A comparative analysis has been conducted of the 4 different cases for the following criteria. These are (i) their governance model, (ii) the co-created value, and (iii) the sustainability vision. Each observation consists of a brief analysis followed by a short interpretation of the feedback provided by the interviewees for a European partnership. We have in particular addressed the observations that may be of direct interest for the future Partnership on SFS, FutureFoodS, and any large initiative in this field. The observations also received a 'Roman number' because these, together with observations-recommendations in the work packages are summarized in Chapter 6.

1.1. Governance

Observation 1: The larger the geographical scale of the partnership, the lower the number of categories of actors represented (I)

The geographical scale effect appears very clearly in the number of actors' categories represented and actively involved. Categories of actors are private (farmers, (artisanal) manufacturers, start-ups, SMEs, large nationals, multi-nationals...), public (local, regional, national, European, and global), academic, philanthropic, NGO, civil society, etc. The Milan Case (MC), a local initiative, is the most inclusive since it is the only one that also includes citizens next to all other categories. Then, the regional partnership Pôle Mer Méditerranée (PMM), serving the regional blue economy, gathers academic organizations, local NGOs and banks, and other public and private actors that are related to or impacted by blue economy activities. The national initiative Foodwest, being economically driven, represents companies, research, and a few public institutions. Finally, the cross-countries partnership BIOEAST includes two categories of actors: national ministries and academic organizations.

➔ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

Through the four in-depth case studies, a correlation appears between the geographical scale of the partnership and the number of categories of actors represented or actively involved. While lower-scale operating partnerships deal more with specific problems encountered by on-the-ground actors in their daily lives, larger-scale partnerships cover general objectives and are more focused on political, or sector-broad, decisions. For larger-scale partnerships, the complexity is further increased since it requires the active presence of a representative of a single category in each European country; sometimes, these representatives cannot even be identified since a thematic area is not defined (or e.g. more broadly formulated 'the bioeconomy')¹. Still, then, it could evolve in time to widen the partnership, like for BIOEAST. For now, only research and politics are represented but it is planned that the private sector becomes involved in the future, due to its important role in innovations.

It should be noted that **the diversity of actors implies a diversity of opinions and ideas that could be potentially inspiring** and serve as a source of inspiration and innovation. On the other hand, **it increases considerably the number of partners and it could appear as a burden in terms of organizing activities**. The structuring of the organization of partnerships should, thus, get full attention, like the role of leaders at different levels of the organization (board of directors, thematic and task groups, communication, and technical/administration services). They ensure smooth communication throughout the network and ensure the mobilization of members around specific themes of 'partnership' activities.

Finally, the feeling of being a member of a collective initiative could also be considered as a threat that may spread among partners. For example, there is the **risk that a lonely driver attitude is created that decreases the quality of common actions and decisions taken**.

Observation 2: Every partnership is led by one actor's category in particular (II)

¹ This observation will require more discussion in the future. For example, one may argue to 'start small' and grow bigger - either on scale (e.g. Neighborhood scale is small, but stakeholder groups big) or participation (e.g. Few stakeholder groups at first and then add more categories). However, 'starting small and growing big' may evoke feelings of exclusion on the way - e.g., 'why weren't we included from the beginning?' and 'why should we come in at a later date?'. Here a direct link can be made with 'value proposition that may change over time'

This observation is related to the context and history of the initiative, as well as to which actor launched the initial idea. In the case of MC, the Cariplo Foundation is considered as leading the MOU-signing process and follow-up activities, since they are strongly involved in the Milan Food Pack from the beginning. For PMM as well as for Foodwest, it concerns an initial request of companies for tools and services that help in reaching better stability, competitiveness, and sustainability outcomes. For BIOEAST, the lead is politically driven to reinforce bioeconomy activities in Central-Eastern Europe.

➔ **Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships**

As evoked in the section analysis above, the apparition of a leader is linked to the history of the partnership, its initial idea, and its commitment to reach – with all actors involved – the objectives that they have stated in the beginning. This holds for all four cases described here, in which a single organization took the lead.

Since administrative and operational activities ask for a substantial and continuous investment in the functioning of a partnership, such a leadership role – by one or a small group of individuals – is crucial and needs to be assumed by one responsible leader.

This leader also needs to **provide a clear vision and overview of actions where the partnership is heading since it needs to be convincing for so many different actors (categories) involved.**

Even more, the link with founders and the connection of the partnership with others outside the partnership **further legitimize the necessity of a representative leader.** Consequently, the process of how this leader is selected and appreciated by the different actors is important to consider. Generally, as observed, the organization is selected which is most engaged in the creation of the initiative. In the cases of PMM and Foodwest, a team has been created that is dedicated to the partnership's ambitions and operations. **Furthermore, important points of vigilance arise concerning communication – from leader to different actors and vice versa – and the relationship between the leading organization and the other partners. A key question is to what extent partners can influence the decision-making process or change the leadership structure itself, if necessary.** If not well addressed within the network of actors representing the different categories of functioning (public administration, academic sector, business, ...) – and laid down in the partnership's binding program documents – the democracy of the governance model is at stake as well as a lasting fair involvement of all actors. The MC case here reveals interesting insights. Concerning a partnership focusing on sustainability outcomes, and, hence, being flexible, adaptive, and exemplary, this issue is fundamental and needs full consideration.

Observation 3: Funding is dependent on the legal status of the partnership (III)

Partnerships, whatever their size and scale, have a big impact on the economy or a specific territory. The four cases have received public funding, at least during their creation phase. Foodwest, being a private company, is now nearly 100% self-financed by selling its services while respecting the objectives stated by the owners/members. Hence, it became quite independent in its decision-making process. PMM, also serving the private sector next to other categories, received most of its funds from the regions. The reason is that it is operating as an association with a non-profit status, i.e. not selling its services. Even if they could do it on some occasions, it is not their objective. BIOEAST and MC are not independent structures but are running thanks to an agreement between involved organizations. They cannot sell their services and are obliged to seek external funds. This is stressed as a barrier to keeping the organization's administration running smoothly. The acquisition sum depends on their scales of operations. BIOEAST has been and is still seeking European funds for projects. MC is partly financed by the partners who signed the MOU (e.g. city of Milan, Cariplo Foundation) and via other private sponsorships.

➔ **Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships**

In all interviews, the availability of funds has been highlighted as a challenging issue. Seeking new funds is a time-consuming activity and each partnership has its strategy on how to get them. **Almost every partnership, except BIOEAST, benefitted from a dedicated fund related to the partnerships' specific**

context². This allowed launching the partnership. Thereafter, strategies had to be adapted to become autonomous while fulfilling (new) objectives. Then, other funders stepped in. Foodwest was the only case in which a lack of external funds didn't cause difficulties. Their business model was built on selling their services; public funds only served as accelerators. The other three cases are not selling services; their objectives were to create new, common, projects. PMM had briefly experienced selling some services, but it took too much time to develop these new activities. Yet, since regional funds continue to decrease, it may become a necessity to sell services soon. Partnerships that have been created within a well-defined, initially mainly public framework (like the Milan Food Pack with its MOU) seem to be more economically stable. They consist of a larger network and include solid funders at the core of their governance model. Starting a partnership from scratch without having other initial financial support than the motivation of partners appeared as delicate and fragile. Interviews conducted within the BIOEAST case highlighted how slow the initiative was developing without sufficient financial back-up. The unavailability of financial means was here considered a serious drawback or barrier. European project funding served to boost the initial development but could not be used for its daily functioning. Finally, funding sources depend both on the objective of the partnership and its initial context. **Mixing different funding sources, and not only relying on public funds, which could fluctuate due to political movements, seems to be a factor of success for a resilient partnership.**

Observation 4: The decision-making process is handled by a small team, governed by a board of partner representatives, and (in)formal processes are suggested to be clearly defined (IV)

All final decision-making processes – the ones that deal with the general strategy or administration of the partnership – are led by a small team, and presided by a specific board. The actors acting on the board mainly originate from the partners involved in the creation of the initiative. Thereafter, it depends on their willingness to open the board to other partners' representatives. In the cases of PMM and MC, partners' representatives and partners are involved in the decision-making process right from the start of the initiative. For BIOEAST and Foodwest, other partner representatives are consulted by the board. Their boards are composed of one type of actor (respectively ministries for BIOEAST and (business) managers for Foodwest) and have final decision power.

➔ **Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships**

The interviews showed **3 different ways of consulting and implicating partners to decide on actions within the partnership**; these are going from the less inclusive to the most inclusive actions:

- **Using outputs of the work done by the partners for expert advice**, extra data (BIOEAST)
- **Involving partner's representatives that have been elected before** by each partner from the different sectors (PMM, Foodwest)
- **Favoring informality** in exchanges to collect partners' feelings and transfer these to the board (Foodwest, PMM) or to decide on daily, on-the-ground actions (MC)

Based on our four in-depth case studies, it is hard to conclude if formal decision-making processes and elections are more – or less – inclusive than those based on informal discussions and agreements. Many of the PMM's interviewees expressed their appreciation of the election process's efficiency which is considered equalitarian and irrevocable. However, it implies that representatives should be able to voice their sector correctly. Informality allows us to collect directly some perceptions and feelings that could not always be voiced during formal open meetings. It may even create tensions with a single partner. Informal decision-making is especially practical for on-the-ground actions that do not necessarily require

² It is worth mentioning that the work of the BIOEAST initiative has been supported from 2019 to 2023 by the Horizon 2020 project **Advancing Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Central and Eastern European countries: BIOEASTsUP**, led by the Polish Institute of Cultivation, Fertilisation and Soil Science. For further reading, please consult: <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/862699>. Currently, the project, that is supporting this initiative, is **HE Boost4BIOEAST - BOOSTing the bioeconomy transformation FOR (4) the BIOEAST region** <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101133398>

a collective decision. Nevertheless, too much informality could lead to a loss of global concertation and drifting away from common objectives; this has been especially noticed by some interviewees of MC. Both ways of communication have their pros and cons and are proposed to be used together. It is what the four partnerships are doing and they are aware of the pros and cons. Since this last point could lead to miscommunications and tensions, **it is thus important to define where formal processes are necessary, where informal exchanges are favorable, and, how it may accelerate or slow down activities.** Transparency in the articulation of recommendations is in all cases primordial because uncomfortable feelings of what takes place behind the scenes build mistrust.

1.2. Sustainable value co-creation

Observation 5: For the four investigated partnerships, benefits from being a partner are rather similar and scale-independent (V)

Jointly creating sustainable value is underlying the existence of all four partnerships. To reach this, networking activities are considered the main target as well as a benefit within all four partnerships. Hence, for each partnership, this is stated as the first objective. The notion and value of knowledge transfer/promotion are also emerging as a priority in all four cases. Another benefit observed both in the Foodwest and PMM cases, is the support for proposal writing and project implementation. Access to the international arena and gaining visibility as a partner in a network have been listed as key values by MC and MPP.

→ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

Networking activities are highlighted as the main benefit for partners. A dedicated person or organization is suggested to take charge of networking activities. Since networking concerns real know-how, time, and energy, each structure may not be able to implement such a task. Common efforts with other structures/partnerships / large initiatives – for example in the context of future joint actions on SFS and even the broader bioeconomy – should here be supported.

This observation is not quite astonishing as creating links between actors remains generally the first goal of a partnership. The fact that it has been reported by so many interviewees within all the cases shows that the four partnerships studied are successful in this sense, hence fulfilling their first objective. Once these new networks are created, the transfer of knowledge is quite consistently considered as the second objective. To create sustainable value in a partnership, this seems imperative to efficiently target; if one is not able to generate a snowball effect with all FS actors, the major objective of a Partnership on SFS may not be reached.

It should be noted that one should pay attention to the nature of networking. As revealed by BIOEAST, this is different e.g. in the implementation of tasks (e.g. resulting from the adopted strategy and partnership program), the functioning of thematic and task groups, the maintenance of relations, the development of networks, or the exchange of information about opportunities in a partnership. Regarding the latter, partners may favor acquiring and deepening knowledge by responding to topics of the SRIA (e.g. focusing on the co-creation of knowledge, and practical solutions...) and/or contribute to maintaining the vitality of the partnership.

Observation 6: A fair sharing of value is required for trust and engagement of participants (VI)

Since this observation is rather straightforward and, thus does not require further explanation, the cases' analysis is not included.

→ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

Even though this observation is rather straightforward, the way to reach this in partnerships may be quite challenging. Some interviewees reported in the BIOEAST case that they are still in the phase of collecting and diagnosing data to develop the partnership strategy. How to create and share value fairly is top

of their mind in this process. Hence, the participants didn't yet reach added value and, thus, are also not yet able to verify if their foreseen way of sharing value is fair.

For the other cases, it is interesting to notice that **fair value sharing is possible in the smaller- and larger-scale structures resulting in equal benefits for the different actors involved. They usually use strategies that help them all access the same services and dedicated public funds.**

Observation 7: Environmental impact and creation of knowledge/know-how are considered the highest added value (VII)

The four studied partnerships focus on either different parts of food systems (food waste, food transformation) or following global strategies (blue economy, bioeconomy). All of them target sustainability in the three dimensions, however, with different weights. The environmental impact is key to all of them. For PMM and Foodwest, a major output is also the direct contribution to the economic stability of their participants/members.

Another major output is the creation of knowledge, both for their members as well as for other areas and sectors within the society; the integration of knowledge in education programs is hereby underlined.

➔ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

A partnership can have a direct or indirect impact on society via its involved actors who seek to maximize the impact of their work. Since a partnership represents collective actions, they will have an impact on the wider society. An example of direct impact is the creation of a new food waste handling chain in the case of MC. Also, fully new actions were undertaken either individually or collectively by partners thanks to the participation in a partnership that was not possible before; for instance, the development of a customer-specific new product in the case of Foodwest, where both producer and customer are members of the partnership.

The indirect positive consequences for society are for example a better management of food waste beneficial for people in vulnerable conditions and, at the same time, improving the city's well-being (the case of MC); another example is the provision of new healthier and more sustainable products on the Finnish and foreign markets in the Foodwest case.

An indirect impact of the partnership on the environment is the inspirational role for others and other (future) projects in society. This point is particularly interesting because it implies that also **the form and functioning of a partnership could be a source of inspiration for others; this may result in the generation of a snowball effect that will be beneficial for society at different levels.** To produce and enhance this effect, **the partnership must be embedded in a wider network and well-connected to outsiders.** All four studied partnerships have such connections in place; some of them have reported that they have been approached for advice by other initiatives or academia.

Finally, the four studied partnerships reveal that they all seek an economic impact. **In a healthy competitive context, these cases demonstrate that the efficiency of cooperation brings more stability, dynamism, and attractiveness of their working area.**

Outcome 8: Raising funds and poor communication are the main barriers (VIII)

For PMM and BIOEAST, raising funds remains a challenge as they highly depend on public funds, which could potentially change with political movements. Poor communication remains a barrier raised by every case (except for Foodwest), including communication with partners, to motivate some partners and coordinate joint activities.

➔ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

Raising funds and poor communication are elements that are necessary for the functioning of partnerships. They are difficult to handle as they depend not only on the partnership's actions but also on the larger context and the behavior of actors. It is important to underline that, **despite these common barriers**

identified, every partnership has a different financing and communication strategy. Indeed, funds could be provided by private or public actors, operating at various scales and obtained by various means (prices, funds, sales). The mix of funds is, generally, unique to each partnership – no one size fits all – and thus creates a specificity of a partnership. Hence, financing strategies should be adapted to the structure and functioning of the partnership as well as its specific context. The same observations can be made regarding communication, which depends on e.g. the type of actors involved, the culture/history of the place, and the character of communication from highly informal to very formal.

This may also partly explain the high diversity of strategies found in the four cases. It is therefore difficult to conclude on a perfect model to adopt. **The recommendation is to have a good overview of all the influencing factors and be flexible to adapt to them; hence incorporate sufficient flexibility in the organizational structure, processes, and functionalities.** The interviews showed that most of the partnerships (at least the older ones) **adapted their strategy through time, to remain flexible to contextual changes and continuously seek new opportunities.** It is suggested to spend sufficient time on different mechanisms that lead to strategic changes in partnerships.

1.3. Sustainability vision

Outcome 9: Cases demonstrate a high diversity of visions, depending on the aim of the partnership and the actors involved (IX)

Some partnerships base their objectives on well-defined sustainability concepts. For example, PMM adopts the blue economy vision and BIOEAST the bioeconomy concept. Partnerships can also be grouped according to other issues. For example, cases such as Foodwest and PMM, which are more focused on private sectors, have a strong technological vision, aiming for product- and technological innovations. The MC is an exception as it deals with organizations at a local scale, aiming to improve the food waste system. The MC has a rather democratic vision, implying various actors occupying the same playing field.

➔ Potential insights gained for FOODPathS and the future Partnership on SFS, as well as for other partnerships

It is noticed that the sustainability vision depends on different factors, e.g. the category of actors that are leading the partnership. For instance, the BIOEAST initiative is led by policymakers. Here, some interviewees reported that the SRIA was too general in its statements, not sufficiently engaging, and sometimes lacking concrete action points. This is of course linked to the scale of the initiative which is quite large, trying to cover all the needs of the countries involved. The risk is that the strategy – and vision – only leads to consensus if they are rather abstract and generic.

Hence, the sustainability vision sometimes comes from a concept that has been defined by representatives of institutions in higher positions. They cannot be easily understood by everyone. However, in other cases like PMM, sustainability has appeared as a necessity by on-the-ground actors sharing the same space and looking directly at the (positive or negative) impacts on the environment or society. **This bottom-up approach seems crucial for determining the sustainability vision and how the different partners will adopt it. It increases the feeling of involvement and commitment in the partnership.**

Other aspects are also to be considered like cultural habits, as they can significantly impact sustainability considerations. Here, communication on sustainability outcomes differed from one country to another. For instance, Finland was rather discrete on this point even if Finnish people have a deep consideration for sustainability; for example, they are considered one of the frontrunners in the bioeconomy.

Finally, **sustainability visions can be determined formally or informally, depending on the scale and the context of the initiative.** Partnerships can adopt a formal definition (e.g. for the bioeconomy and the blue economy) defined by higher institutions, or one that has been informally defined by the actors themselves. Neither one nor the other seems to lead to a better functioning of a partnership. Rather, the adaptability of the vision to the specific context of the partnership appears like an important success factor: **if partners recognize their interests and values in the functioning of a partnership, it seems to increase the level of 'belonging to' the partnership.**

5.1.3. Summary of lessons learned from in-depth case studies

Since the in-depth case studies have provided a wealth of information, we have tried to summarize the main lessons learned in the following figure (presented as a poster at the annual ERIAFF conference).

Figure 6. FOODPathS poster of in-depth case studies outcomes; Source: the authors.

5.2. Major insights on an ideal partnership from a private sector perspective (from WP4)

Some key elements for the Ideal partnership on Sustainable Food Systems

A well-structured partnership for sustainable food systems is crucial to address the multi-faceted challenges in the agri-food sector (D2.1 on mapping of case studies may be consulted (FOODPathS, 2024). Our considerations for the ideal partnership enclose several core features that ensure effective collaboration, governance, and impact.

Why the Agri-food Sector EU Partnership?

The agri-food sector partnership is essential for promoting long-term innovative priorities and inclusive, consensus-based collaboration that reflects the interests of both farmers and the food industry in Europe and its Member States, in particular SMEs. *The partnership is recommended to be instrumental in developing synergies with other programs beyond Horizon Europe, including the Cohesion Funds, the Common Agricultural Policy (CAP), the Digital Europe Program, and the Connecting Europe Facility. These synergies promote the uptake of innovations and amplify their impacts. (X)*

Key Benefits of the EU Partnership, to be taken into account, are:

- **Achieving Critical Mass of Investment:**
Leveraging investments from various stakeholders and programs is crucial in Horizon Europe and more in the next Framework Program 10. This critical mass of investment enables the implementation of large-scale projects and initiatives that individual entities might not undertake independently. **(XI)**
- **Creating European Networks:**
Establishing self-sufficient European networks ensures the long-term sustainability of collaborative efforts. These networks foster continuous innovation, knowledge sharing, and best practice dissemination across the agri-food sector, with the help of the National Food Technology Platforms. **(XII)**
- **Facilitating Dialogue:**
Partnerships provide a platform for continuous dialogues among science, innovation, policy, and education sectors. Interdisciplinary communication is essential for aligning research and innovation with policy priorities and educational needs. **(XIII)**

EU Partnership - Reflections on Key Elements, to be considered, are:

- **Strategic Orientation:**
Partnerships should significantly contribute to the achievements of EU political priorities, such as the Green Deal and digitalization strategies. Aligning with these priorities ensures that the partnership's activities are relevant and impactful. **(XIV)**
- **Common Criteria:**
Throughout their lifecycle, partnerships should adhere to a common set of criteria defined in Horizon Europe Article 8 & Annex III. These criteria guide the selection, monitoring, and discontinuation of partnerships, ensuring they remain effective and aligned with strategic goals. **(XV)**
- **Key Conditions for Launching a partnership**
The existence of a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda/Roadmap (SRIA) is crucial, based on the Food4Life Technology Platform one ex Art 187 TFEU. This document should outline the partners' common strategic vision and should demonstrate their commitment to mobilize resources and investments over the long term (7 to 10 years). **(XVI)**

- **Annual Work Programs**
Translating the Roadmap/SRIA into annual priorities and activities through open calls for proposals is crucial (the implementation plan) This approach ensures that the partnership's work remains dynamic and responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities. (XVII)
- **Systemic Approach:**
Activities should extend beyond research and innovation projects alone. Promoting activities, creating links with other EU partnerships, Actors, and Funds, and engaging in systemic initiatives are essential for achieving broader impacts and fostering sustainable developments within the EU, National and Local agri-food sector. (XVIII)

The Most Important Features of an EU Partnership functioning as a public-private partnership 'PPP' (or: Joint Undertaking), that require detailed descriptions, are the (XIX):

- Legal Structure, which sets the framework for (co-)operation;
- Objectives, reflecting common priorities of diverse actors;
- Membership, which gives a meaning to inclusiveness;
- Financial Contribution, which clarifies the range of possible activities and commitments;
- Governing Bodies (General Assembly, Board of Directors, Technical-Scientific Committee, National and/or Regional Advisors Group, Executive Director, Conciliation and Arbitration Board)

In conclusion, (a) well-designed partnership(s) for sustainable food systems is fundamental to addressing the complex challenges facing the agri-food sector. By adhering to the outlined features and principles, such a partnership(s) can drive meaningful progress toward sustainability, innovation, and resilience in the European agri-food landscape.

5.3. Major insights on the relation between R&I and Education programs and institutions (from WP5)

Research and Innovation (R&I) is a critical resource for the EU in the transformation towards Sustainable Food Systems for People, Planet & Climate. The prime condition for success is that a wide diversity of actors join forces in an EU Partnership – with a mission for change. To achieve this, it is important to link the international networks of institutions of higher education and research (IHER) working on food systems (FS) transition to the other stakeholders involved and invest in several types of knowledge transfer and training on food systems awareness, i.e., supporting the education programs and competence building processes for food system transformation at all educational levels.

In WP5 of the FOODPathS project, we aim to develop a sample charter for institutions of higher education and research that exemplify the role such organisations can play in catalyzing sustainability in food systems.

Therefore, we investigate and learn from existing study programs (curricula; see also D5.1), accreditation systems, and the organization of IHER local ecosystems so that they can motivate staff, students, partners, and citizens to foster Food2030-inspired FS transformations. These are relevant for local/regional communities and reveal the diversity of Member States' solutions. This is also imperative for consistency in EU Research, Innovation, Policy Advice, and Education programs.

In this respect, two major recommendations from Deliverable D5.1 'Assessed skills and knowledge gaps' (FOODPathS, 2024) are:

1. Using Living Labs widely in education programs to experiment with different actors and scholars is requested to be a key attention point of the future partnership(s); (XX)
2. Applying the Pact4Skills model to universities; The joint action model of Pact4Skills, where national, regional, and local authorities; companies; social partners; cross-industry and sectoral organizations; chambers of commerce; education and training providers; and employment services work together can be of value also in a university setting. This variety of stakeholders could contribute to curriculum planning (what is needed), teaching (including site visits), and campus life. A strong cooperation with the Pact4skills program is considered a must for the future Partnership. (XXI)

The research of this study will be further used to help us develop a food systems sustainability charter that focuses on the 4 aspects of what an IHER can do to build an enabling ecosystem for sustainable food systems:

- Curricula development on sustainable food systems
- Public procurement of sustainable food in their canteens and waste management
- Community engagement around sustainable food
- Industry/Research Partnership

This would conceptualize a branded network of EU IHER-driven local ecosystems that can foster improved FS education and training programs, as well as public procurement and citizen engagement, across MS. The developed core principles, criteria, and good practices for the accreditation of FS curricula will be forwarded to support the better functioning of the European research and education invested by the SFS Partnership.

Our first insights are:

- There is an identified gap between the needs of the industry and the offered educational programs Universities are either public or private entities that are confronted with societal

challenges and market demands. The students are partly led by societal considerations and by the labor market in their choice of study and university. The mentioned university ecosystem is therefore not a stand-alone operating factor. It should be seen with multiple other stakeholders. The same goes for the relation between HERI and instance policymakers and/or civil society. Contrary to the interlinkage between stakeholders in e.g. sustainability-oriented initiatives, we also identified that many of these actors work in silos (for instance Food and Health educational programs and/or governmental departments). These interactions may become an essential part of the success factor of the actual catalyze function of the branded network and need extra mapping with support of the future Partnerships. **(XXII)**

- Higher Education Institutions, as independent entities, shape their curricula and sustainability practices based on several factors embedded in the entity's development strategy. Therefore, implementing the principles of sustainable food systems requires a systems approach that identifies the benefits of the transformation. These may be related to opportunities for collaboration, exchange of staff and students, or related to financial support for specific practices. These practices will be developed in the food systems sustainability charter that will be promoted in the SFS Partnership and are suggested to receive strong support. **(XXIII)**

It should be noted that within the range of universities that on paper are exemplary; in reality there will be a wide range of forerunners, followers, or even window-dressers.

- The establishment of a separate organization, a network based on universities, is superfluous when dealing with well-organized, existing networks. The existence of multiple university networks with different motivations calls for further discussion with the actors to come to a mutual concept and identify the use of the networks. For instance, EIT Food, Cleverfood, Fossnet, and FoodPathS have similar approaches but not necessarily the same objectives. Combine these into 1 common objective and approach is a process that needs further coordination, between the networks, including the EC. Here, the future Partnership(s) may play a catalytic role. **(XXIV)**
- the definition of the criteria for being a branded network, and the compliance factors of the organizations applying for joining, ask for a well-thought-through approach. To be inclusive, a training concept should be considered and developed, facilitating HERIs that don't meet the criteria yet but have the ambition to join the branded network. **(XXV)**

5.4. Major insights on Minimizing Trade-Offs and maximizing Co-benefits for an EU sustainable food systems partnership (from WP7):

To move beyond collecting best practices and move towards implementing policies and actions for a broad and deep impact in food systems transformation, we need structured and thoughtfully governed partnerships. Our insights for developing an ideal partnership include aspects to consider related to network building, governance and decision making, funding, and research (please, see also D7.1; FOODPathS, 2024).

Our first observations, research, and conversations with stakeholders showed us that it is important to consider “(un)usual suspects” (XXVI) and to reflect on the point that in European research there is a tendency to communicate and act in particular ways and places, familiar to some and foreign to others. To include more types of groups we have to rethink our ways of thinking & communicating (methods, mediums, levels) and make language universally understandable and relevant.

A *shared vision* can build a strong basis for change. Food systems suffer from unaligned understandings and means for change - if we strive for a different system, aligned visions of how this should look are vital. A shared vision helps articulate co-benefits and trade-offs can be easier to accept since they act as means to an end. (XXVII)

There is *no common definition of sustainable food systems*, but rather the term is used to cover a broad range of topics and indicators, ranging from CO₂- measurement to long-lasting “sustainable” social inclusion. The European Union works with a definition that acknowledges both the essential value of sustainable food systems for climate and biodiversity as well as the economic aspect of income for primary producers and the EU’s competitiveness. *Indicators for sustainability* are closely related to the definition of a sustainable food system. Depending on the definition, many different aspects may be included or excluded in measuring impact. Indicators can help us understand the process of moving toward change and the compromises and synergies along the way.

How we design governance structures has a major impact on who benefits from decisions made. To legitimize and elevate the needs and priorities of all food system stakeholders, it is important to consider who is and is not involved in the decision-making process and to create systems to encourage inclusion and participation. Methodologies for change are frameworks, tools, and techniques to *put inclusiveness into practice*. They range from data-informed guided discussions to bold visioning processes to policy development to holistic planning processes.

Needs and gaps in food systems – as well as the responsibility for change - lie along the whole supply chain. Therefore, solutions will have to react to a variety of needs and all stakeholders will need to respond to their responsibility and be willing to collaborate and compromise.

Our first recommendations fall into three themes: 1) establish fair and realistic representation in governance, 2) work with data, and 3) adapt funding and research priorities.

To establish fair and realistic representation in governance, it is critical to be mindful of power structures; these can build up through money – and funding flows, but also through the capacity for advocacy and when individuals/organizations have multiple roles. To address this, start by co-creating a shared vision

with input from all stakeholders of the supply chain. When doing so, and in ongoing operations of the partnership, acknowledge that work contexts & language use can differ - use understandable universal language or organize in-person stakeholder meetings to enable knowledge transfer and foster understanding (XXVIII).

It is also important that there will be a facilitator or coordinator who can act as a neutral entity between any competing interest groups. To support this role, it is important to *work with reliable data* (qualitative and quantitative) when bringing people together for discussions and decision-making. Non-conventional forms of experiential and indigenous knowledge can be a powerful lever and inspiration (XXIX).

Funding and research priorities need to be adaptable and based on broad stakeholder consultation that takes into account varying needs, challenges, and opportunities. Adaptability can also enable place-based responses to food system transformation that acknowledges regional food behavior. For example, by encouraging the development of networks regionally, nationally, and globally to address solutions along the entire supply chain. Ultimately, adaptability as a key value will enable responses to learn throughout the existence of the partnership (XXX).

5.5. Major insights from 70 + case studies (WP4&7)

For the manual, several elements of FS cases have been extracted from the large number of FS cases studied in WP4 and WP7; these are translated into preliminary recommendations (presented in *italics*). It should be noted that these weren't in-depth case studies (hence not following the interview guide of ANNEX 1) but collected cases known by partners in FOODPathS.

The following elements are worth mentioning here:

- A. The kind of actors and their interactions: in the overall set of food system cases studied, public, private, philanthropic, academic, and civil society organisations were all represented. *Without in-depth interviews with the different actors, it remains difficult to understand 'how actors cooperate around a common objective'. Even more difficult is to estimate how their cooperation contributes to transitions towards sustainability, while often clear indicators have not been defined and monitored. (XXXI)*
- B. The duration of the initiative and its starting date. For our research cases, the majority of cases have lasted, at the time of data collection, for more than 5 years or often far longer, and are still ongoing. *This implies that their 'partnership of very different actors' functions in the long term. (XXXII)*
- C. The location of cases, their geographical dimensions, and spreading about Europe. In our studies, the collected cases cover all scales, however, not equally over scales. The majority of cases studied reveal national and regional scales of operation; this may be due to the partners who collected the cases (often operating at these scales). Depending on the objective, the dimensions are carefully to be considered. *This implies that the creation of 'partnerships' is not bound to one scale; as stated in 'observation 1' above, the number of participants may be scale-dependent (but this is not checked in this deliverable, only for the in-depth case studies. (XXXIII)*

Figure 7: Geographical scale of collected cases. Source: the authors

- D. The type of initiative. Since FS cases may be highly diverse, a consideration of types of cases makes sense. As an example from our case studies, a large variety of types are presented in Figure 7. This list is not exhaustive. Consequently, *'partnerships' may define very different starting points for their initiative, e.g. a policy objective, a potential innovation trajectory, a 'place brand', etc. (XXXIV)*

Figure 8: Type of initiative. Source: the authors

- E. The sustainability objectives of cases: these are shaping the kind of interactions between actors. Here, for our cases, we have differentiated between economic, environmental, and social dimensions of sustainability, but also added innovation, training, and support objectives because of their wide presence in cases. But other differentiations are well possible. This grouping has shown – in the cases that FOODPathS has analyzed – that objectives can be differentiated between those that directly focus on the promotion of one or more sustainability dimensions (economic, environmental, and/or social) of the food system, or indirectly via innovation, education, and support measures. Data has shown that the promotion of innovation has a central place in the collected cases: via research and knowledge sharing, technological advancements (process innovation, digitalization), organizational innovation (clustering, networking), and new markets or policies. Also, it became apparent that there is a strong focus on the economic dimension of sustainability, coupled with objectives directly aiming at supporting the private sector, as a driver of innovation and as an actor of transitions toward sustainability (details can be found in D2.1 and a draft publication). *Still, FutureFoodS or any (a) future partnership(s) is recommended to have the ambition to integrally consider the three dimensions in all supported case studies but may seek an intermediate pathway via innovation, training, or support actions (like CSA's within HorizonEurope).* (XXXV)
- F. Innovation as the driver. Since nearly all researched cases focus on innovation – as strongly supported by public and private (funding) agencies – for the Partnership on SFS, in particular, attention for cross technological, organizational, and social innovations is suggested. *It can be expected that the heterogeneity of outcomes will be substantial; still, targeted interventions at the product & resources level, technology, business, and governance model support are feasible, as cases show. The provision of communication support tools that allow inclusiveness of different actors seemed to be imperative in all cases, and thus a critical attention point in future partnership(s)' supported activities.* (XXXVIa&b)
- G. A broad pallet of activities. A continuous investment in RIPE (Research & Innovation, (science-to-Policy and Education) programs is apparent in most FS cases. *Therefore, it is recommended for the future partnership(s) to combine attention for R&I with P and E. However, also completely other activities should not be overlooked, like design, promotion as well as testing, and demonstrating innovations, as well as activation, management, and development of the*

multi-actor collaborations themselves. The latter requires funding support for networking activities and events and program management in partnerships. (XXXVII)

- H. The used methodology. Primordial for working on and analyzing FS cases is the chosen methodology. It is thus strongly recommended that the methodology should take into account the different elements of an FS case (its context, actors, objectives, activities, etc.). Also, in partnerships with diverse actors, it should be understandable and practically applicable to the different actors involved. Finally, it should permit to structure and analysis of insights in such a way that a future P-SFS can adapt its courses towards sustainability outcomes. Hence, the structure should be widely applicable (XXXVIII). As an example, in FOODPathS, the used methodology has been based on the structure of a game (see Figure XX), because all people are familiar with it, with additional questions about interactions between actors.

Figure 9: The methodology: using the structure of a game for collecting information on case studies, by a variety of actors. Source: the authors, modified from de Vries et al., 2022;

- I. The functioning of the partnership itself. Instead of only supporting activities as a partnership, its functioning also appears as a key attention point in our FS cases. These encompass its capacity to innovate as a partnership, its flexibility in reaching sustainability outcomes, and its capabilities of collaboration and communication, dissemination, and exploitation. Above all, its quality of operating as a collective of different actor groups, speaking a common language, and finding consensus about targets to be reached will distinguish impactful partnerships from others. Hence, it is strongly recommended to (financially) support the functioning of 'partnerships' that are applying for calls of FutureFoodS or any other large-scale partnership/program. (XXXIX)

5.6. Major insights on communicating about the partnership - Exploding the “bubble” (WP8)

What the Partnership does, has a concrete impact on the society (or, if we think to the long-term, for the future generations). Even when actions are aimed at mitigating climate change or restoring the environment, they will have in any case a huge impact on people's lives, in terms of healthier diets, affordability of food prices, access to tasty food produced sustainably, etc. Then, when actors of the food systems are working together to establish the partnership, they must bear in mind that they are acting *for the many*, for any citizen and consumer, as well as for all the other actors of the society that have not been involved in the partnership establishment. Also, because, in the end, the partnership is using resources coming from taxpayers, for whom the partnership's actors should be accountable.

However, what does it mean concretely? It means that the partnership, its activities, and the impacts it is expected to generate must be widely communicated, in a way that can be understood by different actors. The partnership should then take action to go beyond the “bubble” of main stakeholders' representatives and reach a broader audience and, ultimately, the citizens, ensuring their “buy-in”. It is ambitious, indeed, but communication activities tailored to the different target audiences and their needs/motivations can make a difference.

Even if not targeting citizens as a primary target audience (but rather their representatives), FOODPathS can provide some recommendations and lessons learned, based mainly on the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan (D8.1). This document provides an analysis of target audiences, their needs, and activities to reach them, as well as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to monitor, evaluate, and improve the planned actions. However, such knowledge will be integrated during the next months thanks to the results of a survey, that was designed to collect feedback from the societal representatives about the partnership. At the moment, the following recommendations are worth mentioning:

- **Provide a detailed analysis of the target audiences and their motivations and needs (XL):** this is the first step for the definition of messages and activities to engage the different actors. An example of how to carry out the analysis can be found in D8.1. Moreover, attention should be paid to the less represented groups or the stakeholders that are more excluded from the ongoing discussion (i.e., organisations not participating in the partnership creation, entities not conducting lobbying or advocacy activities, smaller organizations, etc.). Only in this way, a wide range of perspectives can be collected, dealing with a broader representation of reality.
- **Based on the analysis, define and implement a variety of actions (XLI):** there is not a single way to reach all the different actors but, as it will emerge from the analysis, rather a portfolio of different communication activities. Social media, webinars, online communities, brochures, press releases, and presentations at conferences are only a few of the possible activities and channels to be used, and only with a mix of them an effective communication be realized. This means adapting also message, tone, and language of each activity, since, as it is easily understandable, talking to policymakers requires a different approach compared to educators. Moreover, even the same activity could be shaped to reach different audiences, according to the message or topic that must be communicated: as an example, in FOODPathS we are realizing webinars, but each of them will target different audiences according to the topic addressed and the message we want to pass.
- **A big challenge requires a common effort: synergies are inescapable (XLII):** to be effective, you must be realistic and acknowledge what are your limits, i.e., in terms of the audience you can reach, scopes of your activities, resources you have, etc. However, there is a way to overcome these challenges and still be committed to generating a greater impact: join forces with others. This is a crucial element in FOODPathS. Firstly, FOODPathS is indeed a *network of networks*: many partners are participating in the consortium because they represent and can leverage networks of stakeholders. Then, FOODPathS is always taking any occasion to join forces with other actors – including other EU-funded projects – to enrich the quality of work and go wider.

An example is the adhesion to the *Food2030 Networks*, an alliance of more than 80 projects established by CLEVERFOOD, that aims to mobilize masses in food systems transformation: thanks to this network, FOODPathS collaborated in workshops to engage stakeholders and collect knowledge from them, contributed to the Food2030 Networks activities and was able to communicate with a wider public. Such kind of collaboration with projects is essential for a partnership, since they can act as “multipliers” of the partnership’s actions.

6. From insights to recommendations

In this chapter, the key elements of the Prototype Partnership are related to recommendations from the four in-depth case studies and the Work Packages 2, 4, 5, 7, and 8. These are structured in the Table below. The latest insights from work currently performed on food system approaches in funding, modus operandi, or science-to-policy processes will be included in the final version of the Manual.

No.	Key element of Prototype Partnership	Short description	Preliminary observations that may be considered relevant for (the future) Partnership(s) from in-depth case studies and work in the work packages (several observations are relevant for more than one element, but only once listed here)
1.	<u>Vision & sustainable value creation</u>	This addresses sustainability consequently from the three dimensions (environmental, social, and economic)	Take into account that benefits from being a partner are rather similar and scale-independent (V)
			Share value fairly for the trust and engagement of participants (VI)
			Consider as the highest added value the environmental impact and the creation of knowledge/know-how (VII)
			Accept a high diversity of visions, depending on the aim of the partnership and the actors involved (IX)
			Contribute to the achievements of EU political priorities and show this (XIV)
			Support a common food systems sustainability charter (XXIII)
			Create and support 'partnerships' at different scales. (XXXIII)
2.	<u>Governance and Legal Status of the Partnership</u>	This incorporates balanced bottom-up and top-down decision-making processes, cross-scales and cross-stakeholder group interactions, and flexibility in structure and functions.	Realize that the larger the scale of the partnership is, the lower the number of categories of actors are represented (I)
			Strive that every partnership is led by one actor's category (II)
			Handle the decision-making process via a small team, governed by a board of partner representatives, and define (in)formal processes (IV)
3.	<u>Co-funding mechanisms & funders forum</u>	This concerns aligning funding strategies of diverse funders while following food system approaches.	Align funding with the legal status of the partnership (III)
			Raise funds and avoid poor communication since they are the main barriers (VIII)
			Leverage investments from various stakeholders and programs (XI)
4.	<u>Modus operandi</u>	Here, collective intelligence and systemic approaches in all operations are favored including human resources, finance, communication, etc.	Adhere to a common set of criteria in the lifecycle of a partnership as defined in Horizon Europe Article 8 & Annex III (XV)
			Demonstrate in an updated SRIA the long-term commitment of participants to mobilize resources & investments (XVI)
			Ensure that the partnership's work remains dynamic and responsive to emerging challenges and opportunities. (XVII)
			Target integrally Legal Structure, Objectives, Membership, Financial Contribution, and Governing Bodies (XIX)
			Define indicators for how actors interact (XXXI)
			Develop or use a methodology that includes different elements of an FS case (its context, actors, objectives, activities, etc.), be understandable and practically applicable for all (XXXVIII)
5.			Support the functioning of 'partnerships' themselves. (XXXIX)
			Use Living Labs widely in education programs (XX)

	<u>Activity areas as defined in the SRIA.</u>	Particular attention is paid to: Sticking to the 4 thematic areas and their links, considering them all from a Food Systems lens (change the way we eat, process & supply, connect and govern), and connecting R&I to science-to-policy advice and Education (RIPE concept). Further elaborating the 4 transversal areas: funding, observatory, Hub of FS labs (working on co-creation cases), and knowledge sharing.	<p>Define very different starting points for researching topics 'partnerships', not just one (XXXIV)</p> <p>Pay attention for cross technological, organizational, and social innovations (XXXVI)</p> <p>Combine attention for R&I with P and E. and don't forget design, promotion as well as testing, and demonstrating innovations, as well as activation, management, and development of the multi-actor collaborations themselves, requiring funding support for networking activities and events and program management in partnerships. (XXXVII)</p> <p>Note: a key issue that has been observed several times: Implement the existing SRIA (https://scar-europe.org/images/FOOD/Main_actions/SFS_Partnership_SRIA_31012023.pdf)</p>
6.	<u>Potential trade-offs and co-benefits</u>	Especially, we have here been involving and taking into account the feedback from Mirror Groups, transition needs from various actor groups, inter-continental conflicting issues, and other ways of knowledge generation such as indigenous knowledge.	<p>Consider "(un)usual suspects" (XXVI)</p> <p>Create a shared vision that articulates co-benefits and trade-offs (XXVII)</p> <p>Use understandable universal language (XXVIII).</p> <p>Use non-conventional forms of experiential and indigenous knowledge as a lever and inspiration (XXIX).</p> <p>Implement adaptability as a key value to learn throughout the existence of the partnership (XXX).</p>
7.	<u>Communication, dissemination & exploitation</u>	The main objective is generating a snowball effect that motivates diverse FS actors to join forces to reach sustainability outcomes.	<p>Align research and innovation with policy priorities and educational needs via interdisciplinary communication (XIII)</p> <p>Provide communication support tools that allow the inclusiveness of different actors in all projects. (XXXVI)</p> <p>Provide a detailed analysis of the target audiences and their motivations and needs (XL)</p> <p>Based on the analysis, define and implement a variety of communication, dissemination and exploitation actions (XLI)</p> <p>A big challenge requires a common effort, hence seek synergies that are inescapable (XLII)</p>
8.	<u>Cooperation with other partnerships,</u>	The starting point is the realization that sustainability outcomes cannot be reached from only a post-farming and fishing perspective and that issues are far too complex to resolve internally, even demanding links with water, energy, health, transport, systems.	<p>Be instrumental in developing synergies with other programs beyond Horizon Europe (X)</p> <p>Establish self-sufficient European networks (XII)</p> <p>Promote activities, create links with other EU partnerships, Actors, and Funds, and engage in systemic actions (XVIII)</p> <p>Cooperate with the Pact4skills program, highly recommended (XXI)</p> <p>Use the catalyzing function of a branded network and invest in mapping (XXII)</p> <p>Play a catalytic role in bringing together science-driven initiatives in EU projects. (XXIV)</p> <p>Facilitate HERIs to join the branded network. (XXV)</p> <p>Invest in long-lasting partnerships that serve as best practices (XXXII)</p>

Table 3: Prototype Partnership elements linked to recommendations based on FOODPathS work

7. Timeline

The timeline provides insights into past activities and events related to the work on preparing the manual for the prototype Partnership, version 1.0

Date	Activities	Events
June 2022	Presenting and discussing the bird as a metaphor for key elements of a prototype	Presenting the bird during the kick-off
June 2023	Getting feedback on the main elements described in the bird image (governance, FS approaches, etc.	The first annual meeting of FOODPathS in Rome, where feedback has been collected from partners and Advisory Board members
July 2023	Integrating feedback in the Milestone 5 'Presentation of Lay-Out of the Prototype P-SFS'	No event, only feedback from the EXCOM members virtually
September 2023 – May 2024	Four in-depth case studies were performed; Internal discussions in work packages	Online interviews and studies; Except for Pole Mer Méditerranée, site visits. For all WPs, different workshops
January – June 2024	Discussions on Ideal partnerships	National Technology Platform meeting & FOODPathS, Barcelona, March 2024 & several FoodDrinkEurope – CopaCogeca meetings in Brussels
June 2024	Presenting in-depth cases and feedback, Presenting all WP outcomes and feedback	World Café session, Annual meeting FOODPathS, Seinäjoki, June 2024
June-July 2024	Finalizing the D2.3 Report	Email exchanges with contributors

Note: In the second half of 2024 and in 2025, the final version of the Manual 2.0 will be realized.

8. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

The following table presents the results of work related to this Deliverable 2.3 (N.A. = not applicable for this Deliverable 2.3). This is done per the KPI categories, as defined in the Description of Activities (DoA) of FOODPathS. The stated targets in the DoA are defined for the end of the FOODPathS project, hence for Month 42.

No.	KPI category	Main KPIs with obtained results	Target*
Out-come #1	Aligned governance & Commitment	(i) level of political & financial commitment to EU, national & local actions: N.A. (ii) percentage of committed EU countries and funding agencies: 15 out of 26 MS = 58% > 26 MS became partners in FutureFoodS (out of the scope of this Deliverable) (iii) inclusiveness via several other co-funders (private, regional,..): several Funder's Forums organized, with substantial participation; some became partners in FutureFoodS (out of the scope of this Deliverable)	75% 75%, (reached) 20+
Out-come #2	Shared visions and actions	(i) level of partner's commitment to a common mission, vision, and strategy: SRIA fully adopted by FutureFoodS; for FOODPathS, all partners and their networks 100% present during annual and other events. (ii) perceived inclusiveness of the governance model by actors: end of project (iii) a percentage of coherently presented best practices: There are over 70 cases presented (see annex), all using the same template;	100% (reached) 100% 100% (reached)
Out-come #3	Mutual Benefits by strengthening local FS actions	(i) number of culturally-specific priorities included in funders strategy: N.A. (this will be done in FutureFoodS); our two joint (annual) meetings with ERIAFF revealed a willingness to share regional-culturally insights (ii) number of functional FS Labs demonstrated by FOODPathS: 5 are explicitly named Living Lab and 10+ are indicated (innovation) Platforms > These will soon be launched via the FOODPathS website by WP4, with input from WP5&7. (iii) percentage of exemplary cases with trade-offs: These are elaborated in the in-depth case studies in WP2,4 and follow-up tasks in WP7	15 (> 150 participants) 10 (reached) <25%, (reached)

It should be noted that for Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation, WP-specific material indicators have been defined, like 'funder info packs', 'interactive maps', etc. These will be reported in WP8 deliverables.

Finally, as stated in the DoA, this project can only provide information for categorized sets of **KPIs with indicative Targets** (a percentage level or fixed number) which are all evolving from 0 at the start of the project³.

Note: the KPI categories linked to impact are too early to discuss here; this will be done in the final deliverables.

³ In a R&I project, KPI can be set for e.g. reduction of waste thanks to the actions carried out in a project. In this CSA, preparing a prototype Partnership, KPI are harder to define since there is no reference line at its start.

9. References and weblinks

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ANNEX I – Background information for interviews in WP2&4

Funded by
the European Union

Background information for interviews

WP2&4

Version May 2023

Funded by
the European Union

The interview process for the in-depth case studies in WP2

- The team will run semi-structured interviews with relevant actors related to the selected case studies. The interviews will follow a semi-structured interview guide (Kallio et al., 2016), with two levels of questions: main themes and follow-up questions. The main themes are few, large, and open questions that cover all the objectives of the research and that will be posed to all interviewees, with exact formulation appropriate to their different roles and knowledge of the initiative. They are formulated and posed in a way to allow the interviewee to feel comfortable and generate spontaneous and in-depth answers. Follow-up questions are asked when needed to make the main themes easier for the participant to understand and to direct the conversation close to the subject of the study.
- Interviews should be conducted through video conferencing software (i.e. Zoom or MS Teams) or face-to-face when possible.
- They will be confidential and anonymized. Interviewees will be cited with their name and function only after explicit agreement and authorization.
- Interviews will be recorded, if so agreed by the interviewee, and when possible. Recording and transcripts of the interviews in the original language will be stored in the Next Cloud of the Partner conducting the interviews and will be only available to the team of the partner.
- Synthetic and anonymized reports of the interviews will be stored on the FOODPathS SharePoint.

The objective of the interviews for the in-depth case studies

- To learn from initiatives driven by the private sector (e.g. clusters, living labs, triple/quadruple helix collaborations) given by WP4's partners
- To explore the notion of living labs and define it further
- To analyze different governance arrangements of multi-stakeholder partnerships for innovations promoting SFS
- To identify the most relevant intermediaries to support SFS and how they could intervene
- To identify value co-creation drivers and distribution within partnerships toward SFS
- To synthesize lessons learned that will constitute inputs for the "virtual showcase" of best practices
- To identify future R&I questions to be addressed by the Partnership SFS

An Email template for the in-depth case studies

– using the AIDA method

Object: Interview for a European CSA project 'Prototype Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems (SFS)', called FOODPathS

Dear XXX

PERSONAL introduction. Because of your connection with XXX, we would like to request 1 hour of your time for an interview. We want to include the ideas, opinions, and experiences of people and organisations like yours in the development of the future Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems.

Are you available on XXX....?

More about the partnership:

The Coordination and Support Action (CSA) FOODPathS, which is being executed by a consortium of 17 organisations under the coordination of INRAE, aims to prepare the ground for the future Partnership on Sustainable Food Systems (SFS).

This Partnership (with an estimated co-funding by the European Commission of ~175M Euro) will play a crucial role in reaching the sustainability ambitions stated in the Farm-to-Fork Strategy and its overarching Green Deal. It will unite many different actors to jointly make the transition towards SFS a success.

More concretely, the CSA FOODPathS is building the prototype of the future Partnership, including the co-design of a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda – SRIA, a governance model, modus operandi, research-innovation-policy-education, and training programs.

If you have any questions about my request, please feel free to ask me in return to this mail or by Whatsapp (+33).

To know more about FOODPathS and the future Partnership:

<https://www.foodpaths.eu/about/#project>

Thank you very much in advance for considering my request,

I look forward to hearing from you,

Background information about FoodPathS to share with the interviewee

*share the following information as appropriate via the invitation to the interview, as an introduction during the interview, or throughout the interview in conversation.

Overview of FoodPaths:

Current discussions and perspectives regarding the characteristics and priorities of a sustainable food system are plentiful, both globally and at a European level. Providing nutritious food while reducing negative environmental impact, strengthening social fairness, and ensuring food security has become a crucial challenge for our future. Interactions between all actors are necessary to address these challenges, overcoming the barriers that may arise due to their different perspectives and interests.

FOODPathS is a project funded by the European Commission that aims to offer a concrete pathway and necessary tools to support the establishment of the European [Partnership for Sustainable Food Systems for People, Planet & Climate](#), to be launched in 2024 based on the experience gained during the project's lifetime. To ensure all voices are heard, the project engages actors from across the food system to create the framework in which the Partnership will operate.

The Consortium is working to co-create:

The **Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)** for the future SFS Partnership, inspires diverse actors to respond to future calls for funding and innovative projects.

The **concepts for co-creation and definitions** allow FS actors to share a common language and fruitfully work together.

A **Hub of Food Systems Living Labs** to overcome current fragmentation and show exemplary SFS cases in an accessible and interactive way.

A **Food System Observatory** for monitoring the sustainability performance of food systems

Education and training programs through a network of higher education institutes working in food systems that train the experts of the future and serve as sustainable playing grounds for emerging new ideas.

Future funding mechanisms and strategies that can maximize the impact of Research and Innovation towards SFS by gathering experiences and expertise of a Network of Funders.

Interview framework for the Living Lab interviews in WP4

Checklist before beginning the interview

- Document(s) to sign?
- Clarify the FOODPathS project and the interview's objectives if necessary
- Remind the time of the interview
- Permission to record the interview

Interview conditions

Name of the interviewer:

Organization:

Date of the interview:

Type of interaction (online/phone/face to face (precise the place):

The first information to collect

Name and number of the case the interviewee is related:

Name of the interviewee:

Position:

Organization:

Role of the organization within the partnership (partner, advisory board...):

Contact information:

Questions (5 main themes and various follow-up questions)

1. (information about the initiative) Can you share with me what you know about the initiative? How and when did it start? What does it consist of / how does it work? How has it evolved in time?
 - a. Who was the initiator of the initiative? Was it a public or private initiative?
 - b. What is the main (common) objective/goal/ambition?
 - c. What types of products and/or services does the initiative offer and for whom?
 - d. What kind of benefits or (economic, environmental, social) value is it creating beyond products and/or services?
 - e. What are key activities (until now and for the future)?
 - f. What are key (technological, financial, human, etc.) resources?
 - g. How will these activities and resources contribute to reaching the objectives?
 - h. When will the initiative be considered a success or failure (based on which criteria or indicators)?

2. (leverages and barriers) What were the key leverages for the success of the initiative? What main problems did the initiative encounter?
 - a. What has facilitated your participation in the initiative?
 - b. Have you encountered any obstacle/problem/barrier to your participation?
 - c. Did you have to adapt to become a partner in the network (hire some people, share responsibility on an asset, co-fund an action, ...)?

3. (Governance) Who are the members of the network and how do they collaborate?
 - a. Who are the main (public, private, other) actors and partners of the network? How do they work together (contracts, joint investments, mutualized equipment, etc.?) What are the drivers and what are the enablers for this collaboration? How are risks, responsibilities, revenues, and costs, (if any) shared...?
 - b. Which interactions are crucial between actors to reach this common objective?
 - c. How are decisions taken in the initiative (either formal or informal)? Has this method changed over time? Why/how?
 - d. How are the members committed to the mission?
 - e. How, when, and under which conditions do you admit participants in the initiative? Has this method changed over time? How/why?

4. (intermediaries) Within the project/partnership/initiative, are there any actors that have helped to facilitate interactions between partners and/or partners' connection with the outside?
 - a. What is the structure allowing playing this role? (name of the structure, type of structure [research center, consulting agency...], nationality, realm of activities)
 - i. How did this structure and its functions be involved within the project/partnership/initiative? Has this structure been hired or is this structure also part of the project/partnership/initiative?
 - ii. At which moment was this structure involved?
 - b. What are their activities within the project/partnership/initiative? (such as developing strategic agenda, setting up networking events, project management...)
 - c. How is this structure perceived by the other partners? (very essential to create a link or it could have worked as well without it)
 - d. **If no structure is present:** How has the project/partnership/initiative managed to create links between participants and the outside world? (embodied by the project/partnership/initiative leader, in co-management...) and
 - e. Do you think using an external actor could have been useful to facilitate communication and relationships?

5. (value creation and capture) What do you think are the key benefits/ key values generated by the initiative?
 - a. What benefits have you drawn from participating in the initiative? In terms of innovation or other benefits?

- b. How does it bring new/ different value to your activity?
- c. How did it maintain and strengthen your core activities?
- d. Do you think the benefits are distributed equally among participants? Or do you think some actors profit more than others?
- e. What do you think are key benefits or values generated for the society at large (environmental, social, economic)?
- f. How can actors use or profit from the value co-created?